

Crack Mitigation at the End Region of Prestressed Concrete Beams using Shape Memory Alloys

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Abstract:

The transfer of high prestressing forces during the de-tensioning of pre-tensioned concrete bridge girders occasionally triggers splitting cracks in the middle of the height of the web at the end region. Especially with the increasing demand for deep-height girders, the web region experiences higher tensile stresses during prestress release, pushing the limits of conventional transverse reinforcement for damage mitigation. In this study, a novel prestressing material, shape memory alloy (SMA), is investigated as a means of preventing web cracks. An experimental setup is designed to apply an eccentric load by replacing the prestressing strand with an actuator. Reduced-scale specimens representing the girder's end region reinforced with either transverse steel or SMA reinforcements are tested to investigate the SMA's effectiveness in improving the cracking strength of the web. Results show that the prestressing force provided by the SMA bars increases the cracking load of the specimen by up to 85%.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pre-tensioned concrete (PC) beams with I- or Bulb-tee (BT) shapes are commonly used in long-span structures such as bridges. These beams employ numerous prestressing strands in the wide flanges, while narrowing the web to improve stability and reduce costs. However, with the high prestressing forces applied to the beams, it has been reported that tensile stresses develop in the end region due to the eccentricity of the prestressing locations and geometric deformations under concentric loads (Fenwick and Lee 1986; Dunkman 2009; Steensels et al. 2019; Shin and Yu 2018). Especially in deep beams, tensile stresses might initiate splitting cracks in the end region, which serve as paths for corrosive materials to penetrate, thereby affecting the structure's capacity or degrading its durability (Darmawan and Stewart 2007; García-Segura et al. 2017; Zhang et al. 2022).

Several studies investigated reinforcement designs to overcome the cracking in the end region of PC beams. Transverse reinforcement with compact spacing is a general option to endure damage in the end region during prestress release. Several experimental and analytical studies explored the range of tensile stresses generated in PC beams by prestress release and suggested an adequate rebar amount in the area (Breen et al. 1994; Gergely and Sozen 1967; Marshall and Mattock 1962). In the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) Load and Resistance Factor Design (LRFD) Specifications (AASHTO 2024), it is recommended to place a minimum rebar requirement at the end region of more than 4% of the total prestressing force, with a 20 ksi stress limit in end region transverse reinforcement.

Recently, due to the constant demand for PC beams with deep sections (i.e., BT-72, IL90, FL96, and NU2000) and larger-diameter strands (i.e., 0.6 in.), employing traditional reinforcements is facing a limit (Ronanki et al. 2017; Ross et al. 2014). In this study, shape memory alloy (SMA) is explored as a new type of transverse reinforcement at the end region to prevent crack propagation. SMA exhibits the shape memory effect (SME), where when SMA is deformed beyond the elastic limit and then heated, it recovers its original shape. Using the SME, SMA bars can introduce thermally-triggered prestressing force in concrete members. The effectiveness of SMA transverse prestressing reinforcement in mitigating web cracking at the end region of concrete beams was evaluated experimentally in this study.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Design of Specimens

The performance of SMA transverse reinforcement in reducing end region damage was experimentally evaluated using two specimens with a symmetric I-shape representing the end region of a beam, as shown in **Figure 1**. The specimen was planned to be fixed at the top flange (T) and loaded at the bottom flange (B) with 3 ft spacing as per lab conditions. To fix the specimen on the ground and apply load on the bottom flange, the specimen was rotated 90 degrees, with the fabrication limited to the end region. Considering the placement of confinement bars and stirrups with their fixing positions, the specimen length was designed to be 45 in., per the AASHTO type III girder design. Following the end region definition of the PC girder in AASHTO LRFD (AASHTO 2024), the specimen height, representing the beam's end region, was designed to be 11.25 in., which is one-quarter of the specimen length (45 in.). To facilitate the manufacturing of specimens, flanges were shaped identically, following the bottom flange design of an AASHTO type III girder with a 16 in. flange width and a 11.5 in. flange height. The first specimen (**Figures 1(a)** and **(c)**) was reinforced in the transverse direction using steel rebars, while the second specimen (**Figures 1(b)** and **(d)**) included a combination of SMA and steel bars. The SMA bars used for transverse reinforcement had a diameter of 0.24 in. with a prestressing level of 40 ksi when fully activated. Steel reinforcements also followed the diameter of the SMA bar, using #2 Grade 60 bars. In the steel specimen, transverse reinforcements were spaced at 3 in., whereas in the SMA specimen, the third reinforcement layer was eliminated to evaluate whether prestressing from SMA activation can reduce the required reinforcement

while improving the structure's performance. The first two layers of transverse reinforcements were substituted with SMA bars to magnify the prestressing effect in the end region. During specimen testing, six strain gauges were attached to the surface of the girders at the top of the web, where cracking was expected under loading. Strain gauges monitored the prestressing effect by SMA activation and crack propagation during specimen loading. The ends of the SMA bars were bent 40 degrees to be tied to the confinement bars, and copper sleeves were crimped to the surface along the SMA bar length to enhance the bonding of the smooth SMA bar with the concrete. In the SMA specimen, although confinement bars were both at the top and bottom flanges to tie them with SMA bars, confinement bars were assumed to have a negligible effect in preventing splitting cracks at the web of the specimen.

Figure 1. Details of the test specimens

2.2 Experimental Test Setup

A test setup was designed to assess the web crack resistance of each specimen with steel or SMA transverse reinforcements. Due to limited laboratory conditions, the specimens were fabricated without the introduction of prestressing strands. Instead, an eccentric load was applied to the flange to replace the prestressing force as shown in **Figure 2**. By rotating the specimen 90 degrees and placing the top flange on a steel plate, the test setup enabled the specimen to experience tensile stresses in the web region, which imitates the stress resulting from the in-plane bending of the web at the end region during prestress release. By fixing the top flange and applying loads at the bottom flange, cantilever behavior was estimated to induce cracks in the web at the top surface of the specimen.

Figure 2. Test setup

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Activation of Shape Memory Alloy Bars

Figure 3 shows the testing procedure for SMA activation using induction heating, with strain gauge measurements taken after heating the SMA until full activation and cooling to room temperature. SMA activation was conducted using an induction heater from the side faces of the specimen, with the top layer heated first and then the bottom. As shown in **Figure 3(c)**, the compressive strain measured at each strain gauge (from S1 to S6) was $62\mu\epsilon$, $20\mu\epsilon$, $103\mu\epsilon$, $60\mu\epsilon$, $71\mu\epsilon$, and $41\mu\epsilon$, respectively. More compressive strain was built near the top surface of the specimen, with the highest at the S3 and S4 locations. The first layer of strain gauges showed an average compressive strain of $78.7\mu\epsilon$, and the second layer showed $40.3\mu\epsilon$. Based on a linear assumption, the compressive strain at the extreme top fiber was calculated to be $86.4\mu\epsilon$, corresponding to a prestressing force of 650 psi.

(a) Induction heating of SMA bars

(b) Compressive strain at the strain gauges after activation

Figure 3. SMA activation results

3.2 Loading Test Results

Figure 4(a) shows the strain variation of steel and SMA specimens at the strain gauge where the initial and main cracks propagated during the loading phase (S1 for the steel specimen and S3 for the SMA specimen). For the steel specimen, cracking occurred at an applied load of 2.7 kips, with a measured strain of $168\mu\epsilon$. The load was applied up to 3.6 kips to observe the specimen's residual behavior. Concrete cracking was observed at four spots (C1 to C4) with a maximum crack length of 9 in. (crack width is 0.015 in.). In the SMA specimen, a single crack was observed at the mid-height of the web under an applied load of 5.0 kips and a strain of $209\mu\epsilon$. The crack length was 9.5 in. with 0.05 in. width at the top, narrowing down to 0.015 in. The results indicate that prestressing transverse SMA reinforcements increased the initial cracking load by 85%, which is desirable for mitigating splitting cracks in the web during prestress release. Even with the third reinforcement layer removed, the SMA specimen showed better crack resistance, demonstrating the effectiveness of SMA stirrups in reducing congestion in the end-region reinforcement design.

(a) Strain variation during loading at initial cracking regions

(b) Crack pattern of the steel specimen (unit: in.) (c) Crack pattern of the SMA specimen (unit: in.)

Figure 4. Loading test results

3.3 Theoretical validation

To validate the experimental results, based on the schematic load and reaction diagrams (**Figure 5(a)**) and the bending moment diagram (**Figure 5(b)**), it was assumed that the cracking moment is 22.6 times the applied load for the given specimen condition. The compressive strengths of the steel and SMA specimens were measured as 10.9 ksi and 9.9 ksi, respectively, using the cylinder compression test. According to ACI 318-25 (ACI 2025), the tensile strength of the steel and SMA specimens was determined as 0.78 ksi and 0.75 ksi, respectively. Using the section analysis, the cracking moment of the steel specimen was calculated as 66.1 kips-in. By dividing 22.6 by the cracking moment, the theoretical cracking load was determined to be 2.9 kips. For the SMA specimen, the prestress from SMA activation (0.65 psi) was added to the concrete tensile strength, yielding a cracking moment of 117.6 kip-in. and a cracking load of 5.2 kips. The experimental and theoretical results showed differences of 8.3% and 4% in steel and SMA specimens, respectively, proving the accuracy of the theoretical interpretation.

(a) Load and reactions

(b) Bending moment diagram

Figure 5. Theoretical approach for calculating the cracking load

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to propose an innovative method to mitigate end region damage during prestress release by applying transverse prestressing with SMA reinforcement. The crack development in the girder's web was experimentally investigated to evaluate the effectiveness of SMA reinforcement using a test setup that applies an eccentric force on the web. Using two SMA stirrups at the end region increased the cracking load from 2.7 kips to 5.0 kips (85% increase) compared to the specimen with two steel stirrups. Replacing steel stirrups with SMA stirrups enabled eliminating the third stirrup layer, reducing congestion, while increasing the cracking load. Theoretical validation showed accuracies of 8.3% and 4% for steel and SMA specimens, respectively, compared with the experimental results.

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